

**Getting to the Root of Things:
The Role of Epistemic Motivation and Construal Levels in Strategic Problem Formulation**

Chan Hyung Park
Olin Business School
Washington University in St. Louis
St. Louis, MO 63130
chanhyungpark@wustl.edu

Markus Baer
Olin Business School
Washington University in St. Louis
St. Louis, MO 63130
baer@wustl.edu

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Abstract

When formulating strategic problems, managers and executives routinely overlook relevant causes. This oversight, in turn, compromises the effectiveness of solutions and strategies. To illuminate the factors determining the success of problem formulation, we develop a model of the individual-level drivers of problem formulation comprehensiveness—the number of nonredundant and relevant causes to a problem individuals identify. Specifically, we theorize that epistemic motivation—the desire to learn and hold well-informed views of the world—is an important driver of comprehensiveness. Furthermore, we suggest that high construal levels—an abstract thinking style—enhance the benefits of epistemic motivation because they direct individual information processing away from the symptoms of a problem towards its underlying causes. We test this interaction model in two experimental studies involving Chinese top executives and university students in the U.S. The results of our two studies are consistent with our theoretical model. High construal levels strengthen the effect of epistemic motivation, resulting in greater comprehensiveness of problem formulation. We discuss the implications of our work for theory and practice.

Introduction

Problem formulation is the “single most important routine” for managers and leaders (Mintzberg et al. 1976, p. 274, see also, Drucker, 2018, Nickerson and Argyres 2018, Rumelt 2011). Problem formulation, or the identification of nonredundant, relevant causes to a problem given its observable symptoms (Baer et al. 2013), matters greatly because how well a problem is formulated determines the value of subsequent solutions and strategies. Problem formulation is especially critical for strategic problems—problems that tend to be complex and ill-structured. Given their characteristics, the probability that strategic actors overlook relevant causes of such problems is high compared to less complex or more familiar problems (Mitroff and Featheringham 1974). To the extent that strategic problems are “wrongly” formulated, the value of strategies that are developed to solve them degrades. Thus, one of the great challenges in solving strategic problems lies in their formulation (e.g., Lyles 1981, Lyles and Mitroff 1980, Mitroff and Featheringham 1974, Nickerson and Zenger 2004, Volkema 1983).

Effectively formulating strategic problems is difficult for most actors, however. According to the behavioral theory of the firm (Cyert and March 1963, Gavetti et al. 2012), strategic actors are boundedly rational. Boundedly rational managers have limited mental capacities and tend to operate with limited information under time constraints. To cope with these limitations, they typically rely on simplified cognitive maps—“cognitive representations”—when dealing with problems of increasing complexity (Gavetti and Levinthal 2000). To the extent that these cognitive representations identify the central causes that comprehensively explain the observable symptoms of a problem, these representations can help discover valuable solutions and strategies. However, individuals tend to simplify complex problems (1) by focusing on obvious symptoms rather than the underlying causes or (2) by focusing on only a few, select causes or even irrelevant causes rather than analyzing the problem situation comprehensively (Axelrod 1976, Dörner 1980, Dörner and Kimber 1996, Simon 1972). Unfortunately, solutions and strategies that respond to the symptoms of a problem or address only a select number of causes will not effectively address a strategic problem. When a problem is formulated narrowly, strategic actors essentially operate with rudimentary cognitive maps of a problem space, which limits the number of

causes and potential solutions they consider. Such a limited understanding of a problem can lead to locally optimal but globally ineffective solutions (e.g., Camuffo et al. 2020, Levinthal 1997).

When problems are formulated comprehensively, managers are more likely to identify central as well as peripheral causes. Previous research established comprehensiveness (exhaustiveness and thoroughness) as the criterion to evaluate the effectiveness of the overall strategic process (e.g., Fredrickson 1984, Fredrickson and Mitchell 1984). *Problem formulation comprehensiveness* is more specific and refers to the number of nonredundant, relevant causes of a problem that organizational actors identify, such that the entire problem space is canvassed as much as possible, given the limits of human rationality (Baer et al. 2013). Comprehensive problem formulation allows actors to form superior representations of strategic problems that more likely identify their root causes. Indeed, previous research has shown that such representations result from a broad survey of complex problem spaces and the diagnosis of the central, alternative factors contributing to the problem—i.e., comprehensive problem formulation (see Gavetti et al. 2005, Rivkin and Siggelkow 2003). The identification of central causes of problems, in turn, is key to the development of superior strategies that focus efforts on resolving the causes that are responsible for or explain most, if not all, of the symptoms.

We examine problem formulation at the individual level of analysis because problem formulation, at its core, is a cognitive process that occurs in managers' minds (Felin and Zenger 2009, Nickerson and Zenger 2004). Despite the importance of problem formulation, existing work does not provide any guidance on which factors determine and enhance comprehensiveness at the individual level of analysis (Nickerson et al. 2007, Posen et al. 2018). Indeed, while past research has lamented the challenges that strategic actors face in formulating complex, ill-structured problems (Baer et al. 2013, Simon 1972), it does not offer insight into the factors that allow them to overcome these difficulties.

We offer such insight by developing and testing a model of the antecedents of problem formulation comprehensiveness. The rationale underlying our model is embedded in the literatures on epistemic motivation and construal levels. Boundedly rational individuals often lack the desire to think carefully about complex problems because doing so requires cognitive effort (Dörner 1980, Dörner and

Kimber 1996, Simon 1955, 1991). Thus, *epistemic motivation*, defined as the drive to learn and hold well-informed views of the world (Amit and Sagiv 2013, Kruglanski 1989), is likely to be critical in propelling individuals to engage and wrestle with strategic problems. The defining characteristics of strategic problems are their complexity and the absence of existing solutions or criteria by which to evaluate the effectiveness of solutions *ex ante*. Epistemic motivation is likely to enhance the comprehensiveness with which actors formulate strategic problems because, instead of jumping to solutions based on a limited understanding of the problem, epistemic motivation propels actors to build a more nuanced and accurate understanding of the problem situation before rushing to action (De Dreu et al. 2000, 2006, Livi et al. 2015). In addition to its significance for problem formulation comprehensiveness, epistemic motivation can be induced, rendering it practically relevant (e.g., Scholten et al. 2007).

Our second claim is that *how* individuals think when formulating strategic problems can strengthen the effect of epistemic motivation on problem formulation comprehensiveness. Specifically, we argue that *high construal levels* (i.e., thinking in more abstract as opposed to concrete terms) (Trope and Liberman 2010, Wiesenfeld et al. 2017) will unleash the full potential of epistemic motivation for enhancing comprehensiveness. High construal levels allow people to transcend the here and now to look at the “big picture,” and process information at a higher level of abstraction and flexibly across domains (Rim et al. 2013, Trope and Liberman 2010). Thus, high construal levels should aid epistemically motivated managers to focus on the theories explaining underlying causes rather than on the symptoms of the problem or its concrete solutions.

Epistemic motivation and construal levels are assumed to result from both dispositional and situational factors (Mussel et al. 2016, Wiesenfeld et al. 2016). Given that situational forces partly shape them, both epistemic motivation and construal levels vary across time. We use an experimental approach to temporarily induce epistemic motivation and alter construal levels in our participants. Consistent with our arguments, the results of our two experiments show that shifting participants’ thinking to a higher level of construal strengthens the effect of induced epistemic motivation, resulting in greater comprehensiveness.

Our primary contribution is that we offer and test an individual level model of problem formulation comprehensiveness. Despite its importance, strategic problem formulation has received limited systematic scholarly attention. Consequently, the problem finding and solving perspective and the problemistic search literature both lack a theoretical model of the factors that determine the extent to which strategic actors engage in this activity and succeed in it (Nickerson et al. 2007, Posen et al. 2018). We integrate the literature on epistemic motivation, construal levels, and problem formulation to identify key drivers and theorize how they interact to impact problem formulation comprehensiveness.

More broadly, our model offers insights into the microfoundations of strategy—or the behaviors, interactions, and cognitions that influence strategic outcomes (Felin et al. 2015). A central assumption in the behavioral view of the firm (Cyert and March 1963) and the behavioral strategy literature (Powell et al. 2011) is the notion that individual level microfoundations aggregate to the organizational level to shape firm strategies and outcomes (March and Olsen 1975). In particular, actors' mental representations of strategic problems are considered key determinants of firm performance as strategic actors tend to be central to developing strategies in their firms (Csaszar and Levinthal 2016, Drucker 2018, Gavetti et al. 2012, Mintzberg et al. 1976). Given that one route to superior, holistic representations of strategic problems can be found in the comprehensive formulation of problems (Gavetti et al. 2005), our model provides insights into the cognitive underpinnings of superior strategies.

Strategic Problem Formulation

The goal of strategic problem formulation is to identify nonredundant and potentially relevant causes of a complex, ill-structured problem based on an observable symptom or a set of symptoms (Baer et al. 2013). A symptom may be a decline in revenue, an erosion of company morale, or any other cue that signals the presence of a deeper problem. Symptoms are the more visible and concrete aspects of a problem, so they are often the main source of information when trying to understand and solve problems (Cyert and March 1963). However, symptoms of strategic problems are “ill-structured” before problem formulation. That means that the underlying causes and their interactions are unknown, and solutions to address the causes are yet to be discovered (Fernandes and Simon 1999, Simon 1991). Complex, ill-

structured problems typically have many underlying causes, requiring a range of different and often novel solutions, forcing actors to make thoughtful decisions about what the causes are and which strategies to implement (Baer et al. 2013, Nickerson and Zenger 2004).

The Deepwater Horizon oil spill is an example of a complex, ill-structured problem that was not easily formulatable and for which no solution existed at the time of its occurrence. Like other strategic problems, the oil spill manifested via visible symptoms (oil and gas escaping the ruptured well) and not via its underlying causes (precise damage to the well), which often remain unobservable. To make matters worse, some relevant factors were likely to interact but the precise interactions were not known *ex ante* (e.g., water temperature interacted with escaping gas). In addition, existing solutions are often inappropriate for strategic problems, given the unique combinations of factors involved (e.g., a containment dome, which had worked in shallower water failed when gas combined with cold water to form crystals that blocked the dome). For such problems, even the criteria by which to evaluate new solutions are not yet agreed upon or established. Finally, the effectiveness of any solution can only be observed over time, and the relevant parameters of the problem may change over time (Camillus 2008, Rittel and Webber 1973, Nickerson and Argyres 2018). So BP could not simply engage in a trial-and-error approach and learn from feedback. The nature of the problem did not remain stable and any feedback would have become quickly outdated and irrelevant.

Given the complexity and ill-structuredness of the problem, BP had difficulty comprehensively formulating it. The consequences of a lack of comprehensive formulation became most obvious when BP invited members of the public to submit their ideas for sealing off its ruptured well and cleaning up the oil that had escaped into the ocean. Around 123,000 people responded from more than 100 countries with potential solutions. Despite the volume of ideas, most, if not all, of the ideas turned out to be unusable because relevant causes were not identified and evaluators could not identify which ideas would effectively solve the problem (Acar 2019). As strategic problems often have some element of complexity and ill-structuredness, some scholars maintain that the central task of managers and leaders is problem

formulation rather than problem-solving, which is often delegated to mid-level managers or low-level employees (Drucker 2018, Mintzberg et al. 1976, Nickerson and Argyres 2018, Rumelt 2011).

Strategic problem formulation is considered comprehensive when all symptoms characterizing a problem can be explained by a set of underlying causes, such that each cause explains at least one of the symptoms (Baer et al. 2013, Nickerson and Argyres 2018). Comprehensiveness ensures that managers develop alternative theories about their causes in explaining the available symptoms, thereby increasing the odds of identifying the most central and relevant causes to a problem (Baer et al. 2013). If actors establish only a narrow formulation of a strategic problem, then the number of strategic options they can consider decreases, and the probability that the problem will be resolved satisfactorily declines. Comprehensiveness is not a sufficient condition for successfully resolving or addressing strategic problems, however. The development and successful execution of strategies are also fraught with difficulties and, in the end, may even depend on luck (Rittel & Webber 1973). Nonetheless, comprehensive problem formulation is one safeguard strategic actors have against prematurely concluding that the most obvious cause of a problem must also be its most critical.

The behavioral view of the firm provides support for the notion that comprehensiveness is central to the development of effective strategies in the context of complexity (Gavetti et al. 2012). This view suggests that strategic problems are difficult to address because strategic actors are boundedly rational and operate under time constraints, with limited information and cognitive capacities (Cyert and March 1963, Simon 1991). To effectively solve these problems, individuals need to meaningfully simplify or represent them by highlighting the central factors that should be considered in their resolution (March and Simon 1958). Consistent with this observation, previous simulation studies found that superior problem representations that enable better, more valuable strategies result from actors broadly surveying problem spaces and identifying the key causal factors contributing to a problem (Gavetti and Levinthal 2000, Gavetti et al. 2005, Rivkin and Siggelkow 2003, Siggelkow and Rivkin 2005). One way to achieve these superior representations is via comprehensive problem formulation that broadly surveys visible parts of the problem space (i.e., symptoms) and identifies the set of underlying causes producing the web of

symptoms (Baer et al. 2013). Thus, comprehensive problem formulation can generate superior representations of strategic problems, thereby allowing for the development of more valuable strategies that concentrate resources on the most central causes of a problem.

Drivers of Problem Formulation Comprehensiveness

Despite the importance of comprehensive problem formulation, its individual-level drivers remain unknown. Much of the literature on problem formulation has highlighted why people *perform poorly* when analyzing strategic problems. Previous work suggests that people prefer not to engage in the cognitively demanding task of formulating complex problems (e.g., Axelrod 1976). Instead, boundedly rational individuals prefer to apply simplifying heuristics to identify the most obvious causes or focus on the symptoms of complex problems rather than investing the effort to uncover hidden, distant causes (Simon 1955, 1972). Or, they may make the (wrong) assumption that there is one cause that explains the entirety of the problem (i.e., single cause fallacy, Dörner 1980, Dörner and Kimber 1996).

As a consequence, individuals often jump to solutions prematurely without comprehensively formulating strategic problems (Bhardwaj et al. 2018, van Hiel and Mervielde 2002). Having to entertain multiple, alternative theories on the causes of a problem is uncomfortable, so reaching closure by jumping to solutions allows people to escape this state of discomfort (Webster and Kruglanski 1994). Although the literature on problem formulation has provided valuable insights, it does not identify the factors that allow individuals to ameliorate these tendencies that hinder successful, comprehensive formulation of strategic problems. We identify two microfoundations that potentially drive comprehensive problem formulation—epistemic motivation and high construal levels.

Epistemic motivation. Motivation is closely linked to the goals people adopt and influences both the amount and direction of effort individuals put into achieving these goals (Ryan and Deci 2000). When trying to formulate strategic problems comprehensively, individuals are likely to benefit from a type of motivation that directs their efforts to build a more holistic and sophisticated understanding of the problem situation rather than focusing on its symptoms, most obvious causes, or solutions. For this reason, we propose epistemic motivation as a central driver of strategic problem formulation

comprehensiveness. Instead of focusing on deriving ad hoc and superficial explanations to quickly resolve the problem, epistemically motivated people are driven to invest the time and effort needed to gain a more nuanced and accurate understanding of a complex situation (Amit and Sagiv 2013). Epistemic motivation is unique in that it compels individuals to engage with and develop a deep understanding of complex problems, regardless of the problems' idiosyncratic characteristics or the problem solver's interest in the problem. Thus, this type of motivation is valuable across problem situations. Given the direction of their efforts, epistemically motivated individuals should be particularly apt at comprehensive problem formulation, as they should be less likely to use simplifying heuristics in the face of complexity or to engage in satisficing.

The construct of epistemic motivation has received widespread attention, particularly from scholars interested in understanding how to curtail heuristic thinking (De Dreu et al. 2000, Nijstad and Oltmanns 2012, Ten Velden et al., 2010). The level of epistemic motivation a person experiences at any moment results from both dispositional and situational factors (Mussel et al. 2016). According to lay epistemic theory (Kruglanski 1989)—a theory that describes the origins and consequences of epistemic motivation—there are a variety of constructs that serve as the dispositional underpinnings and situational drivers of epistemic motivation. *Dispositional underpinnings* of epistemic motivation include need for cognition (“individual's tendency to engage in and enjoy effortful cognitive endeavor,” Cacioppo et al. 1984, p. 306), need for closure (“individuals' desire for a firm answer to a question and an aversion toward ambiguity,” Kruglanski and Webster 1996, p. 264), openness and conformity values (stable drives to “independently explore, discover and learn new, original paths” and to “express self-restriction, order and resistance to change,” Amit and Sagiv 2013, p. 107), and need for structure (tendency to seek “structure and clarity in most situations,” Thompson et al. 2013, p. 20). Need for cognition and openness values are positively correlated with epistemic motivation because they reflect the desire to wrestle with novel and complex issues and to form independent opinions. On the other hand, need for closure, need for structure, and conformity values are negatively correlated with epistemic motivation because they are

related to heuristic thinking and the preference for simple explanations of complex phenomena—regardless of how inadequate these explanations may be.

The most widely studied *situational driver* of epistemic motivation is process accountability. Process accountability is also the preferred way to experimentally induce epistemic motivation (e.g., De Dreu et al. 2000, De Dreu et al. 2006, Scholten et al. 2007, Ten Velden et al. 2010, Van der Schalk 2010). Process accountability refers to “having to account for the ways in which judgments and decisions were reached” (Scholten et al. 2007, p. 341). Process accountability increases the need for people to be rational and provide sound justifications for their reasoning to explain and defend their thought processes to other rational actors (Lerner and Tetlock 1999). As a result, previous research has found that process accountability reduces the tendency to ignore alternative possibilities or viewpoints (e.g., De Dreu and van Knippenberg 2005, Sedikides et al. 2002). Other situational drivers that reduce epistemic motivation include time pressure (Nijstad and Oltmanns 2012) and external threats or noise (Livi et al. 2015). Time pressure reduces epistemic motivation by limiting the time available for individuals to build anything more than a rudimentary understanding of a problem situation. Similarly, external threats or noise increase the urgency to reach conclusions and reduce the desire to engage in systematic, reflective thinking, thereby encouraging the use of cognitive shortcuts (Livi et al. 2015).

Given the nature of strategic problems, a rich understanding of such problems almost always requires the identification of multiple, alternative causes. As the primary goal associated with epistemic motivation is to gain a richer understanding of a complex situation, epistemically motivated individuals are more likely to entertain different and perhaps novel theories about the causes of a problem. Indeed, experiments have found that epistemic motivation prevents heuristic, trial-and-error approaches to problem-solving (Van der Schalk et al. 2010) and instead increases individuals’ willingness to entertain multiple different possibilities before taking action (Federico et al. 2016, Ten Velden et al. 2010). Furthermore, high epistemic motivation increases individuals’ attention toward external information and the willingness to modify one’s beliefs upon obtaining new evidence (De Grada et al. 1999, Livi et al. 2015, Sparkman and Blanche 2017, Van Kleef et al. 2009). The motivation to gain a more accurate and

nuanced understanding of a given situation should drive strategic actors to consider a wider range of information, apply different lenses when digesting such information, and reflect on possible alternative causes rather than accepting the most obvious explanations. In contrast, actors who lack epistemic motivation feel greater discomfort with complexity and tend to use existing and perhaps outdated models of the world in the service of quickly finding solutions (Maysseless and Kruglanski 1987). Thus, we propose that epistemic motivation should provide actors with the drive to formulate strategic problems comprehensively.

Hypothesis 1: *High epistemic motivation will be positively related to problem formulation comprehensiveness.*

Moderating role of construal level. The effect of epistemic motivation on problem formulation comprehensiveness is likely to be regulated by *how* managers think about the problem. Indeed, performance is a multiplicative function of both motivation and relevant tools or skills (Porter and Lawler 1968). Construal levels, or the levels of abstraction with which individuals engage in information processing (Trope and Liberman 2010), represent one such cognitive tool. Strategic actors operating at a high construal level are likely to be better at integrating information and diagnosing underlying, abstract causes than actors operating at a low construal level, obsessing over details and getting “stuck in the weeds.” To provide an analogy, epistemic motivation is akin to the engine in a car, and construal levels are akin to the various gears in a gearbox. The engine determines whether the vehicle moves, but the gears determine how fast the vehicle will move. A powerful engine is rendered less effective if the vehicle is stuck in second gear (i.e., low construal level). However, the engine can achieve the greatest speed once in top gear (i.e., high construal levels). Thus, we propose that the level of construal with which strategic actors approach a problem has implications for how comprehensively they will formulate it, conditional that they are epistemically motivated.

Construal level theory has robust theoretical and empirical foundations in the neuroscience, psychology, sociology, marketing, organizational behavior, and strategy literatures (for reviews, Trope and Liberman 2010, Wiesenfeld et al. 2017). As cognitive styles, construal levels are theorized and

studied largely as situational variables. While dispositional correlates may exist, they are yet to be discovered (Wiesenfeld et al. 2017). The theory's core argument is that construal levels influence how people process and interpret information. People at a higher construal level process information in a way that is "abstract, schematic, and decontextualized, capturing superordinate characteristics of targets," while at a lower construal level people attend to more specific, contextualized characteristics of targets (Reyt and Wiesenfeld 2015, 742). People who are at a greater cognitive, physical, spatial, or social distance from an object tend to think more abstractly about the target—they see the "big picture" or the "forest." In contrast, people at lower construal levels see the "trees" and peripheral details. In the context of problem formulation, the various causes producing a problem constitute the abstract, superordinate characteristics of problems. The symptoms of a problem—its visible indicators—represent the more detailed and contextualized characteristics of problems.

High construal levels should allow epistemically motivated individuals to achieve greater problem formulation comprehensiveness by (1) allowing them to focus on the most central, abstract causes of a problem and (2) increasing their cognitive flexibility to think of alternative causal explanations. Suppose individuals are entrenched in a narrow, concrete view of the problem (e.g., a purely symptomatic view of a problem) and fail to step back and look at the problem from a greater cognitive distance to see the broader picture. In this case, they are likely to fail at identifying the different and distant causes that underlie the problem, even though they are highly motivated. Indeed, scholars have noted that the inability to think about multiple abstract and distant causes across domains constitutes one of the core challenges people face when formulating problems (Dörner 1980, Dörner and Kimber 1996). High construal levels can prevent people from getting stuck on the concrete symptoms of a problem. As Trope and Liberman (2010) note, "the very function of high-level construals is to enable people to transcend the here and now by forming a representation consisting of the invariant features of the available information." Indeed, in six experiments, Fujita et al. (2006) found that individuals operating at high construal levels pay greater attention to the more important goals or priorities. High construal levels

should thus shift people's attention toward the superordinate and central factors (causes) of a problem rather than toward its symptoms.

Furthermore, high construal levels should facilitate the generation of alternative causal explanations, which are central to increasing comprehensiveness of problem formulation. Individuals who operate at higher construal levels are more likely to enjoy greater cognitive openness and flexibility, which should allow them to extract more insights from novel and potentially conflicting information (Jia et al. 2009, Mueller et al. 2014, Rim et al. 2013). This evidence suggests that high construal levels function similarly to a cognitive elevator that provides people with a 10,000 feet view of a problem situation, allowing for the identification of relevant causes across domains and alternative, novel explanations that can account for various combinations of symptoms. By generating integrative, alternative explanations, epistemically motivated individuals operating at a higher construal level are likely to be better at avoiding local optima and finding a global optimum (i.e., root causes) (Liberian and Trope 2014). Based on the arguments above and the available empirical evidence, we hypothesize that high construal levels should strengthen the effect of epistemic motivation on problem formulation comprehensiveness.

Hypothesis 2: *High construal levels will strengthen the relationship between epistemic motivation and problem formulation comprehensiveness.*

Methods and Ethics Statement

We conducted two randomized, controlled experiments, one with a sample of Chinese top executives and the other with students from a Midwestern university in the U.S. We chose to conduct randomized experiments to control theoretically extraneous factors and detect causal relationships (McGrath 1981, Shadish et al. 2002). We gained IRB approvals for the two studies. All participants were above 18 years of age and volunteered to participate in the studies, consenting to the studies before participating in them. Participants were also free to leave as they wished and joined the studies at their chosen time and place.

Experiment 1: Participants and Study Design

Experiment 1 employed a 2 (epistemic motivation: low vs. high) \times 2 (construal level: low vs. high) between-subjects design, involving Chinese top executives of public and private organizations in the agriculture sector. Participants were all taking part in a Chinese university's leadership training program. The training program lasts three months and trains leaders on topics related to leadership, finance, marketing, among others. The goals of the program are two-fold—to help leaders of China's agriculture industry and to provide opportunities for researchers to study the leaders of the agriculture sector.

Although some may argue that the agriculture sector is rather stable and its leaders may face familiar and well-defined problems, this is not true in China. In China, the agricultural sector is less mature and consolidated when compared to the sector in more developed countries. Many farmers in China follow traditional agriculture practices that date back to the Maoist era. As a result, the agricultural industry has fallen behind other nations in terms of technology (Unger 2016). For the past several decades, China's land policy prohibited farmers from consolidating farms (Boyang et al. 2014, Long 2014), preventing farmers from achieving economies of scale. In recent years, Chinese leaders have taken drastic steps to change rural regions and disrupt the traditional agriculture industry through its central planning (中央一号文件) and government policies (“互联网+”现代农业三年行动实施方案). Problems in the industry typically center around poverty and lack of education, rudimentary financial systems, limited resources of local governments, the Chinese central government's policies, among others.

Our sample consisted largely of top executives who managed small to mid-sized organizations. The average revenue of the organizations in our sample was roughly 10 million USD, and the average number of employees was 69. Nearly half of our participants were in top management positions (e.g., CEO, Chair of the Board) in either public or private firms; the other half was divided into top managers of family-owned enterprises and leaders of government-run organizations in rural regions.

A program assistant at the university sent out the Qualtrics link that contained the experimental materials to 300 participants, 134 of whom accepted our invitation (men = 77.61 %). This response rate

(44.67 %) is higher than the rates in similar studies involving top executives of Chinese firms (e.g., Atuahene-Gima and Li 2004, Li and Atuahene-Gima 2001). The average age of the group was 38.22 years, with a standard deviation of 7.14. The average organizational tenure was 6.99 years, with a standard deviation of 7.42. There were no significant differences in age, gender, and organizational tenure across conditions ($p > 0.10$ for all analyses). The experimental materials were presented in Chinese, and two native Chinese speakers fluent in English translated the original English content to Chinese. Another individual who was fluent in English and Chinese reviewed the translation for any mistranslation.

At the beginning of the study, we asked people to identify the “most important problem their organization is facing.” After completing the epistemic motivation and the construal level manipulations, participants identified the causes of the problems they had initially identified. Our design prevents our manipulations from influencing the types of problems participants choose. If we had asked participants to select problems after the construal level manipulation, they might have selected more concrete or abstract problems, depending on the condition. Asking participants to choose problems at the beginning of the study ensures that any differences in problems among individuals should be randomly distributed across conditions.

Problems related to personnel issues (人才) were the most common. 21 participants mentioned personnel problems to be their most pressing concern. Some of the causes of the problem include the outflow of young, talented workers to urban regions, the lack of opportunities in rural areas, and low wages. The second most frequently mentioned problem was lack of funding and capital (资金), with 17 participants identifying this as their most important issue. Some of the causes of the problem include the long financial cycle of the agriculture industry, lack of an accessible banking system, and uncertainty regarding the prices of agricultural goods. Less common problems included sales and marketing (销售).

Manipulations

Construal level manipulation. Construal level theory indicates that lower construal levels involve thinking more concretely (i.e., the how) while higher construal levels involve thinking more

abstractly (i.e., the why) (Liberman et al. 2007, Trope and Liberman 2010). Consequently, we manipulated construal levels by asking participants a series of either why or how questions (Freitas et al. 2004), which is the most widely used and validated approach to manipulating construal levels (Burgoon et al. 2013). Specifically, after reading an example (i.e., *why* or *how* to attain life happiness, depending on their experimental condition, see Online Appendix for the English version), participants were asked to follow the same process of asking themselves *why* or *how* they would accomplish two different goals (i.e., achieve success and gain more knowledge). For instance, someone in the high construal level condition might say that they want to achieve success because they want to enhance their status in society. Participants then had to provide a reason for wanting to enhance their status in society, such as their belief in status as key to gaining respect. Then the participants had to provide a final reason why they would want to gain respect. Conversely, someone in the low construal level condition might say that they would achieve success by constantly updating their knowledge and skillsets. Participants then had to provide two additional ways (of increasing levels of concreteness and logically related to the previous answer) to achieve success or gain knowledge.

Consistent with previous construal level research (Wiesenfeld et al. 2017), we strengthened our manipulation by embedding construal level-related language in the task instructions. In the high construal level condition, participants read the following statement: “At the beginning of the experiment, you identified an important problem that your organization is facing. Why do you think the problem exists? What are the underlying causes for the problem?” In contrast, participants in the low construal level condition read the following instruction: “Above, you identified an important problem that your organization is facing. How did the problem occur? What kinds of contexts and factors created the problem?” Both instructions directly encourage participants to engage in causal analysis, albeit at different levels of abstraction.

Epistemic motivation manipulation. We manipulated epistemic motivation via process accountability (De Dreu et al. 2000, De Dreu et al. 2006, Scholten et al. 2007, Ten Velden et al. 2010). Process accountability gives individuals the motive to develop a thorough understanding of a problem

situation because they have to justify or explain their process of analysis and reasoning to a third party. To manipulate process accountability, we emphasized to participants the importance of reflecting on their thought processes and being logical during problem formulation. Specifically, we told 50 percent of participants before commencing the problem formulation activity: “This is not an exam, and there are no right or wrong answers. We just want to evaluate your thought process. We do not want you to feel pressure to write down what you consider to be ‘the right’ answers. A thorough process of problem analysis, however, will require you to reflect on your own thoughts, summarize them and develop them.” Participants in the low epistemic motivation condition did not receive this statement.

Measures

Epistemic motivation manipulation check. We included three manipulation check questions to evaluate the effectiveness of our epistemic motivation manipulation (cf., Scholten et al., 2007): “I felt accountable for the quality of the process by which I analyzed the problem,” “I thought carefully about what the core issues are,” and “I tried to understand my problem better.” All items were rated on a five-point response scale, ranging from 1 = *Strongly Disagree* to 5 = *Strongly Agree*. We averaged responses to create our manipulation check measure (Cronbach’s alpha = 0.83).

Comprehensiveness of problem formulation. Comprehensiveness is the number of alternative and relevant causes of a problem (Baer et al. 2013). To derive our measure of comprehensiveness, we asked two expert coders who were familiar with the agricultural industry in China and who were blind to our hypotheses to count the number of nonredundant and relevant causes participants identified. The two coders converged in the number of causes they counted—the ICC(1) estimate of agreement was 0.82 and the ICC(2) estimate of reliability was 0.90. We averaged the ratings to create our measure of comprehensiveness.

Results and Discussion

Manipulation check. We reviewed participants’ answers in response to the two prompts used to manipulate construal level. We excluded eight participants from the analysis based on this review, as they had not answered some or all of the construal level manipulation questions. When reporting the results of

this study below, we excluded the participants who had not followed our instructions for the construal level manipulation. However, the inclusion or exclusion of these participants did not change the pattern of results.

The manipulation check measure for epistemic motivation indicated that our manipulation was successful. Participants in the high epistemic motivation condition reported a greater level of epistemic motivation ($n = 63$, $M = 4.23$, 95 % CI = [4.03, 4.43], $SD = 0.82$) than participants in the low condition ($n = 63$, $M = 3.96$, 95 % CI = [3.75, 4.17], $SD = 0.85$), according to a t-test ($M_{\text{difference}} = 0.27$, 95 % CL [-0.02, 0.56], $t[123.85] = 1.81$, $p = 0.07$, $d = 0.03$). In addition, the construal level manipulation had no main effect or interactive effect with epistemic motivation.

Hypotheses testing. The distribution of our measure of comprehensiveness ($M = 3.74$, 95 % CI = [3.36, 4.13], $SD = 2.18$) followed neither a Poisson nor a negative binomial distribution. The measure also did not include an excessive number of zeros, with only 12 out of 126 participants identifying no cause at all. Therefore, we treated comprehensiveness as a continuous variable.

Table 1 displays summary statistics for comprehensiveness for all conditions. We first ran a two-way ANOVA, without the interaction between construal levels and epistemic motivation. We observed a statistically significant main effect of epistemic motivation ($F(1,123) = 17.24$, $p < 0.01$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.13$), consistent with Hypothesis 1. Construal level did not exert a main effect on comprehensiveness ($F(1, 123) = 0.70$, $p > 0.10$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.01$). We then ran an ANOVA with the interaction term included. Consistent with Hypothesis 2, the interaction between epistemic motivation and construal level on comprehensiveness was statistically significant ($F(1,122) = 5.93$, $p < 0.05$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.05$). In this model, the main effect of epistemic motivation was significant, ($F(1,122) = 17.93$, $p < 0.01$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.13$) but not the main effect of construal levels, ($F(1,122) = 0.72$, $p > 0.10$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.01$).

Participants in the high construal level and high epistemic motivation condition found more causes than people in the high epistemic motivation and low construal level condition ($M_{\text{difference}} = 1.18$, 95 % CL = [0.08, 2.27], $t(50.73) = 2.15$, $p < 0.05$, $d = 0.54$), people in the low epistemic motivation and

high construal level condition ($M_{\text{difference}} = 2.37$, 95 % CL = [1.32, 3.41], $t(45.30) = 4.56$, $p < 0.01$, $d = 1.14$), and people in the low epistemic motivation and low construal level condition ($M_{\text{difference}} = 1.80$, 95 % CL = [0.52, 3.06], $t(57.00) = 4.56$, $p < 0.01$, $d = 0.73$). Overall, our results indicate that epistemic motivation increases comprehensiveness and this positive effect is especially pronounced at high construal levels. To illustrate, participants who were in the high construal level and high epistemic motivation condition identified 55 percent more causes than those who were in the low construal level and low epistemic motivation condition. These results support Hypothesis 2.

 Insert Table 1 about here

Discussion of Study 1. The results of our first study provide support for our arguments. When formulating strategic problems, top managers who were epistemically motivated identified a greater number of relevant causes underlying the problem when compared to those who were not. In further support of our arguments, we observed that the effect of epistemic motivation on comprehensiveness was amplified when participants approached the problem formulation activity at a higher level of construal as opposed to a lower level. The findings of Study 1 provide some measure of confidence in the validity of our arguments. We observed the effects despite having instructed participants to choose their problem situation, which introduced heterogeneity in terms of the task.

We wanted to replicate our findings with a second experiment to establish the robustness of our results and to address some of the weaknesses of Study 1. In this new study, we made the following improvements. First, given the limited sample size in our first study, we replicated our results with a larger sample offering greater power. Second, rather than asking participants to address their idiosyncratic problems, we confronted participants with the same problem in Study 2. This way, we held constant the complexity and ill-structuredness of the task. Third, we were more conservative in how we manipulated construal levels. Specifically, in Study 2, we manipulated construal levels without changing the instructions. Although embedding manipulations to the instructions is consistent with how construal levels have been manipulated in the literature (Trope and Liberman 2010), this approach did not allow us

to precisely pinpoint whether it was the *why* and *how* questions or the changes in the problem formulation instructions that led to differences in comprehensiveness. Study 2 is more methodologically precise and only uses the *why* and *how* questions to manipulate construal levels. Relatedly, we employed text analysis to further validate the extent to which the *why* and *how* questions shifted the participants' abstraction of cognition.

Experiment 2: Participants and Study Design

Experiment 2 employed a 2 (epistemic motivation: low vs. high) \times 2 (construal level: low vs. high) between-subjects design, involving 275 students from a Midwestern university in the U.S. (men = 50.91 %). The average age of the participants was 19.02, with a standard deviation of 1.02. To calculate the required sample size to attain power of 0.95, we assumed effect size of $\eta^2 = 0.05$ (based on Study 1) associated with the interaction between epistemic motivation and construal levels. Given this effect size, we determined that a sample size of at least 260 participants was needed. We collected data from 275 participants anticipating that some participants might fail the manipulation checks. We randomly assigned participants to one of the four experimental conditions. After consenting to the experiment, participants first completed the construal level manipulation and then the epistemic motivation manipulation. After the manipulations, they completed the problem formulation task.

We carefully chose a complex and ill-structured problem, resembling the strategic problems managers face. The problem we chose was medical noncompliance, wherein noncompliance refers to the refusal or failure to take medication as prescribed throughout treatment. According to some, medical noncompliance constitutes “the most ignored national epidemic” in the U.S. (Scarlett and Young 2016). The causes of medical noncompliance span a wide range of domains, including patient, healthcare system, disease type, and treatment, all of which are related to each other in one way or another. However, little consensus exists as to the root causes of medical noncompliance and how to effectively address them (Hugtenburg et al. 2013, Marcum et al. 2013).

Participants received the definition of medical noncompliance and a list of symptoms indicating medical noncompliance (e.g., patients take more than the recommended dosage) (see Online Appendix).

Then, we asked participants to formulate the problem. Specifically, we instructed participants, “Above, you find examples of medical noncompliance. We would like you to write down the factors that contribute to these behaviors. In other words, what leads to medical noncompliance?” Participants provided their answers in a text box below this instruction. After completing the problem formulation task, they answered questions capturing demographic information. All participants received course credit for their participation.

Manipulations

Construal level manipulation. As in Study 1, we manipulated construal levels by asking participants a series of either why or how questions (Burgoon et al. 2013; Freitas et al. 2004). Specifically, after reading an example (i.e., why or how to attain life happiness, see Online Appendix), participants read one of three prompts (i.e., improve health, performance in school, and communication skills). They then answered “why” or “how” they would accomplish each goal four times. All participants responded to the three prompts, but we randomized the order in which the three prompts were presented. In this study, we chose to use three prompts rather than two to strengthen our *why* or *how* manipulation and because participants were not as time constrained as the executives in Study 1.

Epistemic motivation manipulation. Consistent with previous experimental work and Study 1, we manipulated epistemic motivation by randomly asking half of the participants to be accountable for their process of analysis. We informed participants in the high epistemic motivation condition that, after the experiment was concluded, they would be contacted by a third party and asked to explain their thought processes, the procedures they followed to derive their answers, and their justifications for their conclusions. Specifically, we told participants, “In this study, we are curious about your thought process when analyzing a problem. When working on the following task, please do not feel pressure to find the ‘right’ answers. As a part of the study, a professor may contact you via a short phone call to learn about the rationales behind your answers and your thought processes behind it. Please let us know some times we could contact you next week.” Participants in the low epistemic motivation condition did not receive the instruction; they only received the definition and symptoms of medical noncompliance. During the

experimental debriefing, participants in the process accountability condition were informed that they would not be contacted by anyone and that the instruction was part of the experimental manipulation.

Measures

Epistemic motivation manipulation check. We used four items similar to those used in Study 1 to evaluate the effectiveness of our epistemic motivation manipulation (cf., Scholten et al., 2007). Using a response scale ranging from 1 = *Strongly Disagree* to 7 = *Strongly Agree*, participants indicated their agreement with the following statements: “I felt accountable for the quality of the process by which I analyzed the case,” “In analyzing the case, I thought carefully and deeply about what the core issues really are,” “In analyzing the case, I thought thoroughly about all the potential issues of the situation,” and “In analyzing the issue, I tried to be as comprehensive as possible” (Cronbach’s alpha = 0.83).

Comprehensiveness of problem formulation. Comprehensiveness was again measured via the number of nonredundant and relevant causes (of medical noncompliance) identified by participants. To derive a list of the causes, we first reviewed relevant literature (e.g., Marcum et al. 2013) and public health websites. We then conducted five rounds of pilot studies, each time with nine participants, whom we asked to identify the causes for medical noncompliance. Then, we contacted six master’s degree students from the school of social work and two medical doctors at a Midwestern university to review the coding scheme. The master’s degree students had extensive experience in healthcare and included a former doctor, a former nurse, and former employees of healthcare and biotechnology organizations. The coding scheme we used can be found at the end of the Online Appendix.

Two trained coders blind to the hypotheses reviewed each participants’ analysis and coded the number of nonredundant, relevant causes. The ICC (1) and the ICC (2) estimates of interrater agreement and reliability were 0.82 and 0.90, respectively. Given this level of convergence, we averaged the number of causes identified across the two coders.

Results and Discussion

Manipulation checks. We asked two coders to review participants’ answers to the three prompts used to manipulate construal levels. Based on this review, coders identified seven participants who had

not properly followed our instruction to find deeper reasons or more concrete means when responding to the prompts. When reporting the results of this study below, we excluded the participants who had not followed our instructions for the construal level manipulation. However, the inclusion of these participants did not change the pattern of results we report below.

To further verify the extent to which our construal level manipulation influenced individuals' construal levels, we used the linguistic category model (LCM) on participants' problem formulation responses. LCM is a validated, computer-automated method that evaluates the level of abstraction in language, which can serve as a "window" into individuals' construal levels (e.g., Freitas et al. 2004, Johnson-Grey et al. 2020, Reyt and Wiesenfeld 2015, Semin and Fiedler 1991). LCM is rooted in the idea that different words embody different levels of abstraction, which can be used as an indicator of individuals' cognitive abstraction. For instance, LCM treats more descriptive action verbs, such as "to run" or "to jump" as concrete, while treating the more interpretative verbs, such as "to relate" or "to harm" as more abstract. LCM scores adjectives as most abstract, as adjectives provide the more general descriptions of objects that are valid across different contexts (e.g., agreeable, consistent). Participants in the high construal level condition scored higher in LCM ($n = 134$, $M = 2.19$, 95 % CI [2.15, 2.23], $SD = 0.23$) than participants in the low condition ($n = 134$, $M = 2.09$, 95 % CI [2.05, 2.14], $SD = 0.27$), according to a t-test comparison ($M_{difference} = 0.10$, 95 % CI [0.04, 0.16], $t(259.61) = 3.14$, $p < 0.01$, $d = 0.40$). Thus, our construal level manipulation was successful, as it created a significant difference in the level of abstraction in the language that participants used during the formulation activity.

An analysis of the manipulation check measure for epistemic motivation indicated that the manipulation was successful. Participants in the high epistemic motivation condition reported a greater level of process accountability ($n = 134$, $M = 5.11$, 95 % CI [4.95, 5.26], $SD = 0.91$) than participants in the low condition ($n = 134$, $M = 4.79$, 95 % CI [4.61, 4.97], $SD = 1.08$), according to a t-test comparison ($M_{difference} = 0.32$, 95 % CI [0.07, 0.56], $t = 2.60$, $p = 0.01$, $d = 0.32$). In addition, the construal level manipulation had no main effect or interactive effect with epistemic motivation on this measure.

Hypotheses testing. The distribution of our measure of comprehensiveness ($M = 3.68$, 95 % CI = [3.45, 3.90], $SD = 1.92$) followed neither a Poisson nor a negative binomial distribution. The measure also did not include an excessive number of zeros, with only 11 out of 268 participants identifying no cause at all. Therefore, we again treated comprehensiveness as a continuous variable.

Table 2 displays the summary statistics for comprehensiveness across all conditions. Consistent with Hypothesis 1, a two-way ANOVA without the interaction between epistemic motivation and construal level included revealed a main effect of epistemic motivation ($F(1, 265) = 4.55$, $p < 0.05$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.02$). In contrast to Study 1, we also found a statistically significant main effect of construal level ($F(1, 265) = 31.18$, $p < 0.01$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.11$). We then ran a two-way ANOVA that included the interaction between epistemic motivation and construal level. In support of Hypothesis 2, we found a statistically significant interaction between epistemic motivation and construal level on comprehensiveness ($F(1, 264) = 4.76$, $p < 0.05$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.02$). In this model, the main effect of epistemic motivation was also significant, ($F(1, 264) = 4.61$, $p < 0.05$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.02$) as was the effect of construal level ($F(1, 264) = 31.62$, $p < 0.01$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.11$).

People in the high epistemic motivation and high construal level condition found more causes than people in the high epistemic motivation and low construal level condition ($M_{\text{difference}} = 1.71$, 95 % CI = [1.03, 2.39], $t(132) = 4.95$, $p < 0.01$, $d = 0.86$), than people in the low epistemic motivation and high construal level condition ($M_{\text{difference}} = 0.94$, 95 % CI = [0.35, 1.55], $t(121.41) = 3.14$, $p < 0.01$, $d = 0.54$), and than people in the low epistemic motivation and low construal level condition ($M_{\text{difference}} = 1.70$, 95 % CI = [1.08, 2.33], $t(127.57) = 5.39$, $p < 0.01$, $d = 0.93$). To illustrate, participants in the high epistemic motivation and high construal level condition found 60 percent more causes than participants in the low epistemic motivation and low construal level condition. These results are consistent with Hypothesis 2.

To verify that the level of construal (i.e., abstraction) produced the observed effect, we conducted an additional analysis in which we interacted the level of abstraction of participants' cognition, measured via LCM, with epistemic motivation. Consistent with our primary results and Hypothesis 2, we found a

statistically significant interaction between the LCM-based measure of construal level and epistemic motivation, $F(1, 264) = 4.06, p < 0.05, \text{partial } \eta^2 = 0.02$.

Insert Table 2 about here

Discussion of Study 2. In Study 2, we confronted participants with a complex and ill-structured problem—the problem of medical noncompliance in the U.S. As in Study 1, we observed a main effect on comprehensiveness of epistemic motivation as well as a significant interaction between epistemic motivation and construal level. The results indicate that epistemic motivation increased problem formulation comprehensiveness and that the relationship was stronger when participants approached the problem situation operating at a higher level of construal. We replicated this interaction using the LCM-based measure of construal level, which suggest that it is indeed the level of abstraction that influences problem formulation (in interaction with epistemic motivation) and that the effect of construal level is not simply an artifact of the particular manipulation we used (i.e., asking *how* or *why* questions). Contrary to Study 1, we also observed a main effect of construal level on comprehensiveness—participants operating at a higher level of construal identified a greater number of relevant causes. The result indicates that the precise role of construal levels in problem formulation requires more examination.

General Discussion

The purpose of our paper was to develop and test a model of the individual-level antecedents of comprehensive problem formulation. The empirical evidence we obtained across our two experiments supports our arguments and the interaction model we proposed. This consistency is noteworthy, as the two samples came from different countries with different cultures and involved participants from different backgrounds. In addition, in Study 1, participants selected their strategic problems, while those in Study 2 all solved the same complex, ill-structured problem of medical noncompliance in the U.S. Still, epistemic motivation and construal level had consistent effects—high construal level enhanced the value of epistemic motivation for problem formulation comprehensiveness.

Our research has important theoretical implications. First, our findings extend the problem finding and solving perspective and the literature on problemistic search by offering the first glimpse into the motivational and cognitive factors that determine strategic problem formulation comprehensiveness. The problem finding and solving perspective and the problemistic search literature have emphasized the role of cognition in shaping how strategic problems are formulated and represented (Baer et al. 2013; Posen et al. 2018). However, this work has not specified *which* cognitive factors are particularly relevant and has largely ignored the role of motivation. Our work extends previous research by specifying the type of motivation and cognitive style that enhance comprehensives and examining how they combine to affect this outcome.

Our research also has implications for the literature on the behavioral view of the firm and the work on behavioral strategy more generally. A central argument in these literatures is that actors' holistic mental representations of strategic problems are key to developing superior strategies (Gavetti and Levinthal 2000, Gavetti et al. 2012). However, how such holistic mental representation can be formed remains unclear (e.g., Gavetti et al., 2005). Given that the essence of superior problem representations is the identification of key causal factors that explain the various symptoms of a problem—i.e., comprehensive problem formulation—our model provides insights into the individual level microfoundations that allow strategic actors to generate holistic, superior representations.

Next, we contribute to the research on construal levels (Wiesenfeld et al. 2017). Our theory and results, particularly from Study 1, suggest that high construal levels alone may not be sufficient in determining certain outcomes. In the absence of epistemic motivation, individuals operating at higher levels of construal may rely on existing mental models and abstract stereotypes to narrowly formulate problems rather than generating alternative theories on the different causes of problems. Indeed, recent research suggests that high construal levels can lead people to form general and simplistic conclusions about causes (McCrea et al. 2012; Namkoong and Henderson 2019). Thus, we suggest that the effects of construal levels may depend on underlying motivations, representing an important boundary condition.

Finally, we offer practical guidance on how to generate superior, “big picture” representations of strategic problems. Scholars have noted that strategic actors often experience difficulty in formulating problems comprehensively (Baer et al. 2013, Nickerson and Argyres 2018). Our model offers a possible reason for this—the conditions that give rise to epistemic motivation and high construal level may not be present in many organizational environments. Time is scarce, especially among top-level executives. Yet, time pressure is known to reduce epistemic motivation (Nijstad and Oltmanns 2012). In addition, the need to make decisions or offer actionable strategies often outweighs the desire to invest the time and energy necessary to develop a well-informed and sophisticated view of a problem situation. Thus, even if actors tend to habitually assume a “big picture” view, without having the drive to gain a rich understanding of a problem situation and the time to act upon this motivation, comprehensiveness is unlikely to ensue. Furthermore, it is not uncommon for managers to get “lost in the weeds” of a problem because of their desire to use their existing knowledge and expertise (Bhardwaj et al. 2018). This tendency, in turn, can also compromise problem formulation comprehensiveness. Without a process to instill epistemic motivation, strategic actors are likely to narrowly formulate strategic problems.

To ensure that strategic actors engage problem formulation epistemically motivated and operating at a high construal level, holding them accountable for using a protocol that guides them through the formulation activity might be useful. Such a protocol could separate problem formulation from solution generation, instructing actors to first map out relevant symptoms and then use these symptoms to identify all relevant causes and their interrelationships. This process could be paired with instructions asking actors to clearly outline their thought processes, noting that there are no right answers and asking them to think in terms of “why” while identifying potential causes. Although these instructions may seem trivial, our work suggests that they are likely to have an outsized effect on the comprehensiveness with which strategic problems are formulated.

Our work also has implications for how managers can lead teams charged with strategic problem formulation. Previous research has suggested the use of structured processes to ameliorate some of the barriers to problem formulation at the team level (Baer et al. 2013). Given that process accountability

serves as a tool to induce epistemic motivation, one could imagine that, along with asking a team to deliver a document outlining the causes they identified producing a particular problem situation, the team may also be asked to describe the process of analysis used to derive the various formulations. According to our model, this process should enhance the comprehensiveness with which the team formulates a given problem. Thus, process accountability could be a valuable addition to the design of any structured process aimed at facilitating the problem formulation activity at the team level.

Limitation and Future Directions

Our research has several limitations. First, we should caution that, in some cases, greater comprehensiveness may not be desirable or helpful. When trying to implement solutions or strategies under time constraints, managers who are determined to formulate strategic problems with comprehensiveness may become preoccupied with and distracted by an overwhelming number of causes. Although a certain degree of comprehensiveness may help identify more distant causes and make solution search more efficient, managers who spent an inordinate amount of time and energy on formulating problems with comprehensiveness may lose sight of the fact that analysis has to be balanced with the development and timely implementation of solutions and strategies. Thus, comprehensive problem formulation is likely to be more useful when people engage in this activity in a systematic and time-bound way. Indeed, Csaszar and Levinthal (2016) indicated that allocating too many resources to strategic problem formulation can potentially undermine the quality of strategies. This observation is consistent with the too-much-of-a-good-thing effect (Grant and Schwartz 2011), which states that even good things such as comprehensive problem formulation may have diminishing or negative returns. However, the notion of bounded rationality and recent research both indicate that the more important and widespread challenge in complex problem-solving is not over-analysis of problems but under-analysis even when full information is provided (Rahmandad et al. 2021). Consequently, our primary focus was on how to increase problem formulation comprehensiveness rather than how to restrict this activity. Nevertheless, we see value in future research identifying and examining stopping rules for the formulation activity.

Next, we did not explore the role of information in shaping the effects of epistemic motivation and construal level on comprehensiveness. For instance, if people have detailed information about a problem, they may also think more comprehensively about it. Conversely, such information may shift people's focus to more concrete aspects of a problem, thereby lowering their construal level. Thus, scholars may want to consider the potential role of information in shaping construal level and comprehensiveness. Another possible avenue for future investigations is exploring the role of knowledge. For example, people who have abstract knowledge across multiple domains may formulate problems more comprehensively. Indeed, previous work suggests that having broad knowledge sets can provide people with different perspectives and views of the world and prevent people from getting entrenched in parochial views of the world (Dane 2010, Mannucci and Yong 2018).

Finally, we recognize that our focus on problem formation at the individual level of analysis is limiting. The formulation of strategic problems is often a collective effort, which may unfold in teams (Baer et al. 2013). Nevertheless, our findings may inform research on the composition of teams charged with tackling complex, ill-structured problems. Specifically, our findings suggest that when composing such teams, selecting for the dispositional correlates of epistemic motivation (e.g., high need for cognition and openness values and low need for closure and conformity values) in addition to more traditional selection criteria, such as complementary skills and expertise and compatibility in personality may prove to be efficacious. Future work examining the role of team composition for problem formulation comprehensiveness may thus wish to consider the dispositional underpinnings of epistemic motivation.

Conclusion

How managers can formulate strategic problems with greater comprehensiveness is not well understood. We develop and test a model of problem formulation at the individual level of analysis that spotlights the importance of epistemic motivation and high construal levels for problem formulation comprehensiveness. Two experimental studies with Chinese executives and university students in the U.S. support our arguments that epistemic motivation is a driver of comprehensiveness and that a high

construal level enhances the benefits of epistemic motivation. We hope that our findings encourage additional work on problem formulation and how this important activity can be nurtured in practice.

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TABLE 1

Study 1: Means and Standard Deviations by Condition*

Conditions	Comprehensiveness	SD	Variance
Low Epistemic Motivation, Low Construal Level (n = 28)	$M = 3.30, [2.45, 4.15]$	2.30	5.29
High Epistemic Motivation, Low Construal Level (n = 32)	$M = 3.92, [3.35, 4.49]$	1.64	2.69
Low Epistemic Motivation, High Construal Level (n = 35)	$M = 2.73, [2.26, 3.2]$	1.41	1.99
High Epistemic Motivation, High Construal Level (n = 31)	$M = 5.10, [4.20, 6.00]$	2.57	6.60

* 95% confidence intervals are in square brackets.

TABLE 2

Study 2: Means and Standard Deviations by Condition*

Conditions	Comprehensiveness	SD	Variance
Low Epistemic Motivation, Low Construal Level (n = 67)	$M = 3.07, [2.66, 3.47]$	1.65	2.72
High Epistemic Motivation, Low Construal Level (n = 67)	$M = 3.06, [2.57, 3.55]$	2.00	4.00
Low Epistemic Motivation, High Construal Level (n = 67)	$M = 3.82, [3.46, 4.18]$	1.47	2.16
High Epistemic Motivation, High Construal Level (n = 67)	$M = 4.77, [4.28, 5.25]$	1.99	3.96

* 95% confidence intervals are in square brackets.